

SOCIAL SCIENCES

MILLET FARMING AS A PATHWAY TO SUSTAINABLE LIVELIHOODS FOR TRIBAL FARMERS IN KERALA: CHALLENGES AND POLICY IMPLICATIONS

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Abstract

This study explored the prospects of millet farming as a sustainable livelihood option for tribal farmers in Kerala, India. Utilizing a mixed-methods approach, the research was conducted among 600 tribal farmers in the Idukki district, assessing their socioeconomic profiles, the extent of millet cultivation, engagement with government schemes, and the challenges they face. The findings indicated that millet farming is deeply rooted in the cultural practices of these communities but is primarily pursued for subsistence due to limited market access, financial constraints, and inadequate knowledge of value addition and processing techniques. The study suggested that targeted policy interventions, including enhanced education and training, financial support, improved market linkages, and promotion of sustainable farming practices, are essential to unlock the full potential of millet farming.

Keywords: millet farming, sustainable livelihood, tribal farmers, Kerala, socioeconomic development

Introduction

Millet farming has emerged as a promising avenue for achieving sustainable livelihoods among tribal farmers in Kerala, India, particularly in the face of environmental challenges and socioeconomic uncertainties (1,2). Millets such as finger millet and pearl millet are well-suited to the region's arid and semi-arid conditions due to their resilience, low water requirements, and ability to thrive with minimal external inputs (3,4). These attributes make millet an ideal crop for marginalized tribal communities with limited access to resources and face significant barriers in conventional agriculture. The ecological adaptability and nutritional benefits of millets also contribute to biodiversity conservation and food security, offering a multifaceted solution to the challenges faced by smallholder farmers (5,6). The potential for millet farming to bolster income generation, improve food security, and preserve cultural heritage underscores its relevance in the broader discourse on sustainable agricultural and rural development (7,8).

However, the adoption and expansion of millet farming among tribal farmers in Kerala face several obstacles, including limited access to high-quality seeds, inadequate financial resources, and poor market linkage (9,2). Despite these challenges, there is a growing recognition of the need to support millet cultivation through targeted policies, capacity building, and community-driven initiatives. Government programs and non-governmental organisations have begun to play a critical role in promoting millet farming, though the awareness and utilization of these resources among tribal farmers remain limited (2). Understanding the extent of tribal engagement in millet farming, their access to support systems, and the socioeconomic impact of millet cultivation is crucial

for designing effective interventions. This study aims to explore these dimensions, providing actionable insights into how millet farming can be scaled up to secure sustainable livelihoods for tribal communities in Kerala.

Method

This study employed a mixed-methods approach to explore the prospects of millet farming as a sustainable livelihood option for tribal farmers in Kerala. The research was conducted in *Kizhattoor*, *Marayoor*, and *Kottakomboor* hamlets in the Idukki districts, targeting 600 tribal farmers using stratified random sampling. An equal number of 200 participants were selected from each hamlet. Primary data were collected through pre-tested interview schedules administered face-to-face by trained research investigators, covering socioeconomic profiles, the extent of millet cultivation, livelihood capital, knowledge about and utilization of government schemes, and challenges faced by farmers.

Additionally, focus group discussions were held with various stakeholders, and selected case studies were conducted to gather qualitative insights. Secondary data were sourced from government reports, academic journals, and publications by NGOs working among tribal farmers. Quantitative data analysis was performed using SPSS software and qualitative data analysis was conducted thematically. Ethical considerations were strictly adhered to, including informed consent, confidentiality, and protection of participants' rights.

Results

The study revealed that millet farming holds significant potential for enhancing the livelihood of tribal farmers in Kerala, although various socioeconomic challenges and resource limitations

persist. The analysis indicated that a majority of tribal farmers involved in millet cultivation are middle-aged, with an average age of 45 years. The gender distribution showed male dominance in farming activities (68.5%), although women are actively involved in key tasks like sowing, weeding, harvesting, and post-harvest processing. Educational levels among tribal farmers are notably low, with over 76% having no formal education, limiting their access to advanced agricultural knowledge and market information. Most farmers operate on small, fragmented landholdings, with 67% having medium-sized plots between 1.6 and 3.0 acres, and 22% owning less than 1.5 acres.

Millet farming is practised primarily for subsistence rather than commercial purposes, with only 402 acres out of 1,819 acres of land owned by the households dedicated to millet cultivation. The predominant millet variety grown is finger millet, which is valued for its adaptability and minimal input requirements. Despite the long-standing tradition of millet farming, the study found that knowledge about processing, value addition, and marketing remains limited among tribal farmers, restricting economic benefits. Only 37.5% of tribal farmers reported selling their produce, and market access is constrained by inadequate transportation facilities and low market prices, discouraging commercial expansion.

The financial status of these farming households is precarious, with the average annual income reported at Rs. 26,234. A substantial majority (65.7%) earn less than Rs. 25,000 yearly, highlighting their economic vulnerability and reliance on agriculture as the primary income source. Most farmers (87.5%) engage in agriculture, with many also participating in supplementary activities such as wage labour (49.3%) and foraging (33.3%) to sustain their livelihoods.

The qualitative data underscored the key challenges such as lack of financial resources, limited access to high-quality seeds, and inadequate market linkages. Climate change and labour shortage further complicate farming efforts. While there is strong community support and involvement in traditional millet farming practices, significant opportunities exist to improve productivity and profitability through targeted interventions, such as training on modern agricultural technologies, and infrastructure development for storage and processing. Moreover, the participation of tribal farmers in government programs remains low, largely due to limited awareness and accessibility issues. While some farmers benefit from schemes like *Punarjeevanam*, many are unaware of broader initiatives such as the State Millet Mission.

Discussion

Despite the cultural and economic importance of millet farming, the study revealed several barriers that limit its potential, including low educational attainment, inadequate market access, and insufficient financial resources. Policy implications from this study suggest a multifaceted approach to bolster millet farming among tribal populations. First, improving access to education and training is essential to empower farmers with the knowledge required to adopt advanced farming techniques and navigate market dynamics

effectively. Financial support mechanisms, such as microfinance, low-interest loans, and subsidiaries tailored to small-scale millet farmers, could alleviate financial barriers and facilitate investments in farming activities. Strengthening market linkage by developing cooperatives, enhancing transportation infrastructure, and providing access to market information can help farmers receive fair prices for their produce. Additionally, incorporating millet into the public distribution system (PDS) and implementing minimum support prices (MSP) could provide a stable income for tribal farmers. Lastly, promoting sustainable agricultural practices through government and NGO initiatives, including the distribution of drought-resistant millet varieties, and the provision of infrastructure for storage and processing, will be pivotal in maximizing the benefits of millet farming. These policy measures can collectively contribute to enhancing the socioeconomic resilience of tribal farmers, ensuring food security, and promoting sustainable rural development in Kerala.

Conclusion

Millet farming represents a vital opportunity for sustainable livelihood enhancement among tribal farmers in Kerala, offering resilience against climatic challenges and aligning with traditional agricultural practices. However, this study highlighted that while millets hold considerable potential for improving food security and income stability, significant barriers, including limited education, inadequate market access, and financial constraints, impede the full realization of this potential. Addressing these challenges through targeted policies and interventions such as enhancing educational opportunities, improving economic and market access, and promoting sustainable farming practices can empower tribal communities to leverage millet farming as a cornerstone of their socioeconomic development.

Acknowledgement: This paper was prepared under the Minor Research Project funded by the Indian Council of Social Science Research (F No. 02/185/2022-23/ICSSR/RP/MN/SC dated 21/3/2023).

References

1. Behera MK. Assessment of the State of Millets Farming in India. *MOJ Ecology & Environmental Sciences*. 2017 Mar 3;2(1). <https://doi.org/10.15406/mojes.2017.02.00013>
2. Sreeni KR. Millet Village Attappady, Kerala: Choice for Healthy Food Consumption, Food Security, Livelihood, Income and Employment. *Food Science and Nutrition*. 2023 Feb 3;9(1):1-7. <https://doi.org/10.24966/FSN-1076/100151>
3. Thilakarathna M, Raizada M. A Review of Nutrient Management Studies Involving Finger Millet in the Semi-Arid Tropics of Asia and Africa. *Agronomy*. 2015 Jun 30;5(3):262-90. <https://doi.org/10.3390/agronomy5030262>
4. Serba DD, Yadav RS, Varshney RK, Gupta SK, Mahalingam G, Srivastava RK, et al. Genomic Designing of Pearl Millet: A Resilient Crop for Arid and Semi-arid Environments. In: *Genomic Designing*

of Climate-Smart Cereal Crops. Springer, Cham; 2020. p. 221–86. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-93381-8_6

5. Choudhary S, Singh YK, Vishnu Moond, Dharmendra Bahadur Singh, Kant A, P. Tejasree, et al. Unearthing the Nutritional and Agricultural Value through Scientific Innovation in the Natural Gene Pool of Millets. *International Journal of Environment and Climate Change*. 2023 Dec 27;13(12):1188–201. <https://doi.org/10.9734/ijecc/2023/v13i123783>

6. Gupta N, Srivastava AK, Pandey VN. Biodiversity and Nutraceutical Quality of Some Indian Millets. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences, India Section B: Biological Sciences*. 2012 May 30;82(2):265–73. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40011-012-0035-z>

7. Devi OA, Saikia AR, Ghorband AS, Saikanth D, Badekhan A, Aresh J, et al. Shree Anna (Millets): A

Nutritional and Agrarian Solution to Food Production. *Journal of scientific research and reports*. 2024 Mar 20;30(5):316–27.

<https://doi.org/10.9734/jsrr/2024/v30i51947>

8. Vidhya CS, Girase I, Spandana B, Jejal AD, Singh M, Bahadur R. Enhancing Nutritional Security and Combating Hidden Hunger with Climate-Resilient Millets. *International Journal of Environment and Climate Change*. 2023;13(11):4587–602.

<https://doi.org/10.9734/ijecc/2023/v13i113638>

9. Gopi A. “Tribal Development”- Perspective from Below. *Journal of State and Society [Internet]*. 2023;1(1). Available from: [Journal of State and Society, Vol. 1 No.1 2023 \(researchgate.net\)](https://www.researchgate.net/publication/368111111)